

1 **Combining eight research areas to foster the uptake of ecosystem-based management in fresh**
2 **waters**

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19 ABSTRACT

20 1. Freshwater ecosystems are under a constant risk of being irreversibly damaged by human
21 pressures which threaten their biodiversity, the sustainability of ecosystem services (ESS), and
22 human well-being. Despite the implementation of various environmental regulations, the challenges
23 of safeguarding freshwater assets have so far not been tackled successfully.

24 2. A promising way forward to stop the loss of freshwater biodiversity and to sustain freshwater-
25 based ESS is by implementing ecosystem-based management (EBM), an environmental planning
26 and adaptive management approach that jointly considers social and ecological needs. Responsible
27 for considerable recent success in sustainably managing and conserving marine ecosystems, EBM
28 has not yet been championed for fresh waters.

29 3. A major reason for EBM's delayed uptake in fresh waters may likely be its complexity, requiring
30 planners to be familiar with the latest developments in a range of different research areas. EBM
31 would therefore benefit from becoming more tangible to receive attention on-the-ground.

32 4. To facilitate uptake, eight core research areas for EBM and their innovations are introduced. It is
33 then explained how they feed into a workflow that guides through the EBM-planning stage.

34 5. The workflow links biodiversity distributions with ESS supply and demand modelling, SMART
35 (specific-measurable-attainable-relevant-timely)-target planning including scenario- and cross-
36 realm perspectives, prioritization of management alternatives, spatial prioritization of biodiversity
37 conservation and ESS areas, and the quantification of uncertainties. Given the extensive resources,
38 time, and technical capacity required to implement the full workflow, a light and an ultralight
39 version of the workflow are provided.

40 6. Applied in concert, the eight well known research areas allow better planning, operationalizing,
41 and eventually implementing EBM in freshwater ecosystems. EBM has great potential to increase
42 public acceptance by introducing the consideration of human needs and aspirations into typically
43 biodiversity-driven conservation and management approaches. This will ultimately improve the
44 integrity of freshwater ecosystems.

45

46 KEY WORDS: biodiversity, catchment, ecosystem approach, ecosystem services, river

47 1. INTRODUCTION

48 Freshwater ecosystems contain a diverse array of species and habitats that provide numerous
49 societal benefits. They have been, and still are, under a constant risk of being irreversibly damaged
50 by human demands and pressures, threatening the sustainability of freshwater ecosystems, their
51 biodiversity, the provision of ecosystem services (ESS) and, ultimately, human health and well-
52 being (Bennett et al., 2015). Despite a plethora of environmental directives, regulations, and action
53 taken at regional and global levels, e.g. the Water Framework Directive (WFD; Council of the
54 European Communities, 2000), the Birds Directive (Council of the European Communities, 2009)
55 and the Habitats Directive (Council of the European Communities, 1992) in Europe, or the global
56 Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011-2020 (Convention on Biological Diversity, 2010) which have
57 led to some progress, anthropogenic risks have not yet been tackled satisfactorily (Secretariat of the
58 Convention on Biological Diversity, 2014).

59 A potential way forward to become more successful in managing freshwater ecosystems
60 towards reaching freshwater-bound targets is through the implementation of ecosystem-based
61 management (EBM). There is no single agreed-upon definition of EBM (also referred to as the
62 Ecosystem Approach), but it can generally be understood as a collaborative management approach
63 intended to restore, enhance and/or protect the resilience of an ecosystem so as to sustain or
64 improve ESS and conserve biodiversity, while considering human society as an integral part of that
65 ecosystem (Long, Charles, & Stephenson, 2015). Hence, EBM extends integrated approaches that
66 have been applied to fresh waters in the past, such as Integrated Water Resource Management or
67 Integrated River Basin Management. These management approaches focus on the uses and needs
68 for water and the management of water as a resource through demand management, pricing, water
69 conservation measures, and infrastructure (Juffe-Bignoli et al., 2016).

70 EBM has received considerable attention in the marine realm, where it has been used to
71 develop sustainable fishery strategies, leading to a range of successful management examples
72 (Wondolleck & Yaffee, 2017). Despite its demonstrated success in marine management, EBM has
73 so far not been championed in fresh waters. Their management, however, entails similarly complex
74 and often intertwined interactions between social and ecological factors. Therefore, EBM is likely
75 to be useful in improving freshwater management, for example, for the development of the WFD's
76 River Basin Management Plans (Vlachopoulou et al., 2014).

77 Due to the inherent complexity of ecosystems, and fresh waters in particular, their
78 management is rarely simple or comes with single solutions. Hence, challenges are expected
79 regardless of the approach taken (Waylen et al., 2014). EBM, in particular, has been criticised as
80 being too complex to be effectively applied (Ansong, Gissi, & Calado, 2017). Inarguably, due to its
81 multidisciplinary nature, EBM challenges researchers and planners alike. Those involved have to be
82 familiar with the latest developments in multiple research areas, because science has to

83 acknowledge critical societal challenges, and management can only be effective if it is evidence-
84 based.

85 Thus, this paper aims to strengthen links between EBM theory and practice to foster EBM
86 implementation in freshwater ecosystems, and thereby facilitating the conservation of freshwater
87 biodiversity. To do so, the current status and recent innovations of eight core research areas of EBM
88 are reviewed. The novelty of this paper lies in the explanation of how these eight well-known
89 research areas can be combined into a workflow to support EBM planning that is based on
90 knowledge and collaboration. Since the workflow may require substantial data and resourcing, two
91 less complex versions of the workflow are additionally provided. Although the focus of this paper is
92 on fresh waters - highlighting the untapped potential of EBM in this realm - the workflow is
93 transferrable to other ecosystems.

94

95 2. PLANNING EBM

96 Several components are important when planning EBM. They comprise biodiversity, ESS, external
97 scenarios (i.e. environmental scenarios that consider temporal changes such as socio-economic or
98 governance developments), deficit identification, management strategies, and spatial planning (Fig.
99 1) which link in the following way: Two sets of mapped occurrence layers - one for biodiversity
100 and one for ESS delivery and demand - are the basis of an EBM plan. The choice of biodiversity
101 and ESS depends on the respective freshwater system and the management objective in question.
102 Distributions of these layers are projected into the future based on the external scenarios. The
103 projected distributions are compared with the pre-defined targets to identify the deficits to be
104 accounted for. Knowing the deficits helps develop potential strategies to manage the system.
105 Predictive models for biodiversity and ESS distributions are then used to display the projected
106 consequences of the different management strategies, which allows prioritizing the strategy which
107 is most beneficial for biodiversity conservation and ESS provision. Projected biodiversity and ESS
108 distributions under the optimal management strategy are then used as input layers to spatially
109 optimize biodiversity conservation and ESS delivery areas within the system to be managed. The
110 outcome of the spatial optimization is a plan that informs EBM implementation.

111 In addition to the components that build the EBM plan mentioned above, several notions are
112 crucial for the development of an effective EBM plan: i) Biodiversity and ESS distributions are
113 modelled across aquatic and terrestrial realms, considering connectivity between adjacent
114 ecosystems, ii) external scenarios as well as management strategies are planned together with
115 stakeholders, iii) targets are defined based on environmental regulations, policy recommendations,
116 and stakeholder preferences, iv) an optimal management scenario is identified based on different
117 criteria (including efficiency and equity, and the evaluation of predicted effectiveness of the
118 outcomes) and, v) uncertainties are quantified for biodiversity and ESS models, stakeholder

119 preferences, and for predictions of management strategies, and these are reported to the decision
 120 makers together with the EBM plan (Fig. 1). The second and third notions ensure conformity to
 121 national and international directives and enable community buy-in.
 122

123
 124 **Figure 1.** The conceptual frame for the EBM planning stage consists of different components. Each
 125 component is informed by one or several research areas (indicated by icons). To perform a full
 126 cycle EBM, the EBM-planning stage, which is described in detail in this study, is followed by the
 127 implementation of the EBM strategy, and the monitoring and evaluation of respective outcomes.
 128 New knowledge, which is gained through the implementation and evaluation of the EBM strategy,
 129 feeds back into the different components, allowing for an adaptive process. Detailed information on
 130 how to approach the EBM process that follows the planning stage are, for example, described in the
 131 Open Standards for the Practice of Conservation (<http://cmp-openstandards.org/>).
 132

133 Based on the EBM concept shown in Figure 1, eight research areas were identified that
 134 provide knowledge necessary to operationalize the planning stage of an EBM process. Indeed, the
 135 importance of the eight areas was supported by the fact that each of them has the potential to
 136 integrate multiple EBM-key principles (Long et al., 2015) (Tab. 1). In the following, the eight
 137 research areas are reviewed in the light of how their latest innovations can be used to benefit
 138 freshwater EBM-planning.
 139

140 **Table 1.** The 15 EBM-key principles, listed by decreasing importance (1-15) according to the
 141 literature (Long et al., 2015). Their coverage by the eight research areas (icons are the same as in
 142 Figure 1) is indicated with check marks. Principles 2, 10, and 14 are not covered, since they are not
 143 part of the planning stage of EBM.

EBM key principles		Research areas							
148	1. Acknowledge uncertainty	✓	✓		✓			✓	✓
149	2. Appropriate monitoring								
150	3. Interdisciplinarity	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
151	4. Distinct boundaries	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	
152	5. Decision reflect societal choice			✓	✓		✓	✓	
153	6. Recognise coupled social-ecological system		✓		✓		✓	✓	
154	7. Ecological integrity & biodiversity	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	
155	8. Account for dynamic nature of ecosystems	✓	✓						✓
156	9. Sustainability			✓	✓		✓	✓	
157	10. Integrated management								
158	11. Stakeholder involvement			✓	✓		✓	✓	✓
159	12. Use of scientific knowledge	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
160	13. Appropriate spatial & temporal scales	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
161	14. Adaptive management								
162	15. Consider ecosystem connection	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	

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164

165 2. THE EIGHT RESEARCH AREAS AND THEIR INNOVATIONS FOR FRESHWATER EBM

166 2.1 Modelling species distributions

167 Mapping species distributions (or a comparable taxonomic or functional unit) is a key aspect in any
 168 spatial planning procedure that accounts for patterns in biodiversity and its constituting elements.
 169 Such patterns are often derived from observational occurrence data and/or from expert knowledge.
 170 However, due to the Wallacean shortfall, i.e., the challenge of precisely delineating the distribution
 171 of species, the true distribution range of any species can at best be simulated (Bini, Diniz, Rangel,
 172 Bastos, & Pinto, 2006). Such simulations are possible using species distribution models (SDMs).
 173 SDMs have been widely used in ecology to quantify how environmental and anthropogenic factors
 174 affect species distributions (Booth, Nix, Busby, & Hutchinson, 2014), and are increasingly used to
 175 predict patterns in species distributions under changing environmental conditions. For example,
 176 using SDMs Kuemmerlen et al. (2015) found that future land-use change has a stronger negative
 177 impact on the benthic invertebrate community of the Changjian catchment (south-east China)

178 compared to climate change, while the effects of climate and land-use change counterbalance each
179 other to a certain degree. Consequently, when appropriately used, SDMs can provide the spatially
180 extensive biodiversity information which EBM is based on.

181 Current innovations in SDMs that benefit EBM planning are twofold. Firstly, the increasing
182 diversity, availability, and quality of input data provides many new opportunities. Nonetheless,
183 there is still a paucity of continuous and widespread environmental data providing accurate
184 information on habitat properties at small spatial scales. This hinders the inclusion of highly
185 relevant parameters such as discharge, flow velocity, water temperature, depth, among others, in
186 current freshwater SDMs (Domisch, Amatulli, & Jetz, 2015). Secondly, SDM methods are
187 continuously improving, for example by considering the network structure of rivers affecting how
188 connectivity is spatially implemented (Peterson & Hoef, 2010). The addition of temporally dynamic
189 features provides a promising future direction in improving outputs of static correlative SDMs.
190 Static correlative SDMs are not dynamic *per se*, but distributions can be predicted for several time
191 slices to mimic the dynamic pattern of the models, as done within the terrestrial realm (e.g. daily for
192 migratory birds (Fink et al. 2010) or across decades (Hayes, Cryan, & Wunder, 2015)). Further
193 improvements in this area would be highly relevant for prediction of species distributions over time
194 (Martínez-López, Martínez-Fernández, Naimi, Carreño, & Esteve, 2015).

195 Improvements to addressing the uncertainty of SDM outputs include their correction for
196 biotic interactions which are currently only implicitly incorporated (models and parameter inference
197 are based on current observational data which inherently include effects of biotic interactions), the
198 integration of species movement, dispersal and history, and the effects of genetic differentiation (Qi
199 et al., 2018). For example, Gavish et al. (2017) showed for the benthic invertebrate community
200 from the Kinzig watershed (central Germany) that, in certain cases, SDMs that incorporate
201 surrogates for biotic interactions increase the predictive performance at the species and community
202 levels. Hence, the continued development of SDMs will provide further opportunities for their
203 successful uptake in EBM frameworks.

204

205 *2.2 Modelling ecosystem services supply and demand*

206 Inherent to any EBM is the importance of ecosystems to human well-being and the tendency of
207 social systems to modify ecosystems. These two relationships are connected through complex
208 adaptive processes, which shape the supply and the demand of ESS. Hence to assess ESS
209 distribution, models should represent supply and demand (i.e. providers and beneficiaries of ESS)
210 in order to display the natural and social features between which ESS can flow. Beneficiaries are
211 the social agents that benefit from the ecological processes sustained by providers. Assessing ESS
212 dynamics with explicit consideration of both natural and human components enables the
213 quantification of flows between providers and beneficiaries. As the same variables and subjects can

214 simultaneously participate (in different roles) for different ESS, scenarios can be built where the
215 change of any variable affects all other linked components. This allows the quantification of
216 important trade-offs among different ESS. Such trade-offs could include: hydropower generation
217 versus connectivity of fish habitats, groundwater extraction for agriculture versus maintenance of
218 wetlands and associated biodiversity, water transfers among different catchments versus
219 maintaining minimum ecological flows, natural wetlands as green infrastructures that process
220 nutrients versus using them as recreational areas, among others (Villa, Portela, Onofri, Nunes, &
221 Lange, 2015).

222 Currently, the majority of ESS assessments yield static snapshots depicting proxy values,
223 usually computed on the basis of look-up tables, whose main input is land cover type (Ricaurte et
224 al., 2017). A static snapshot would be, for example, to assign fixed parameters like water retention
225 capacity to a certain land cover type without considering the seasonal supply and demand of water
226 within that watershed. Such assessments disregard the dynamic nature of ESS as assets of coupled
227 social-ecological systems that exhibit complex feedbacks. Hence, although used as a typical ESS
228 mapping shortcut, this approach does not necessarily correspond to a realistic and credible
229 representation of the system's dynamics. This can be problematic especially for ecosystems that are
230 less well represented by proxy land use values, as it is the case for fresh waters. Context-specific
231 models that consider social-ecological processes and their linkages with specific services relevant in
232 time and space, should lead to more holistic assessments (Garcia-Prats, del Campo, & Pulido-
233 Velazquez, 2016; Martínez-Fernández et al., 2014; Nassl & Löffler, 2015).

234 To improve ESS models in the future and therewith ensure successful EBM, we need a
235 better understanding of how biodiversity and ecosystem processes are linked to each other and of
236 their ESS, as well as how changes in the condition of fresh waters impacts the delivery of ESS. On
237 the demand side, it is still quite unclear how individual and collective decisions are affected by
238 environmental changes and how society responds to changes in the supply of freshwater ESS.
239

240 *2.3 Planning with SMART targets*

241 Traditionally, directives and policies relevant for fresh waters (e.g., the WFD and the Habitats
242 Directive) strived to protect selected species or environmental conditions. Consequently, they use
243 targets developed for single-sector management, i.e. for fresh waters. Hence, the current challenge
244 for freshwater EBM lies in defining SMART targets, i.e. targets for objectives that define the
245 amount of a component of the social-ecological system to be reached or conserved and are specific
246 (S), measurable (M), achievable (A), relevant (realistic) (R), and timely (T).

247 Using SMART principles for target setting gained attention when the Convention on
248 Biological Diversity (CBD) developed 20 SMART Aichi Targets (Perrings et al., 2010). Whether
249 Target 11, which is the one relevant for fresh waters will be fully reached by 2020, is still

250 questionable (Juffe-Bignoli et al., 2016). Currently, the target still lacks quantifiable definitions of
251 success (besides the amount of protected area) to evaluate effective, equitable biodiversity
252 management, the ecological representation of a mix of ecosystems, and the connectivity between
253 sites to allow species dispersal (Tittensor et al., 2014). Hence, indicators and current baselines for
254 these targets have to be established to be able to quantify the distance to the defined end-points
255 (Juffe-Bignoli et al., 2016).

256 As EBM becomes more popular, targets and respective indicators are needed for entire
257 coupled social-ecological (freshwater) systems (Levin, Williams, Rehr, Norman, & Harvey, 2015).
258 EBM targets have to reflect freshwater values that society relates to the respective fresh water,
259 along with targets underpinned by regulations which consider the ecology of the system.
260 Developing such targets is complex. For example, anglers may wish for an invasive fish species to
261 be present in a lake, whereas a freshwater regulation requires its eradication. Hence, target setting is
262 best informed by predictions of the consequences of management actions, and how they propagate
263 through the respective social-ecological system.

264 Quantifying societal preferences is an additional challenge in EBM target setting.
265 Participatory decision-making processes, such as those provided by Multi-Criteria Decision
266 Analysis (Eisenführ, Weber, & Langer, 2010), can help structure the process. Reichert, Langhans,
267 Lienert, & Schuwirth (2015) describe how societal preferences can be elicited and included in the
268 decision-making process together with scientific knowledge. Nevertheless, whether a collaborative
269 process will be successful largely depends on the willingness of the involved parties to contribute
270 towards jointly negotiated solutions (Bodin, 2017).

271

272 *2.4 Planning with scenarios*

273 Scenario assessment makes use of alternative data inputs, model simulations, and/or narratives. In
274 EBM the use of scenarios provides stakeholders and institutions with the outcomes of their current
275 decisions and supports collective decision-making through comparing and assessing alternative
276 courses of action. Depending on the need, the use of scenarios can support exploratory, normative
277 or predictive planning analyses (Oteros-Rozas et al., 2015).

278 During the EBM-planning stage, scenarios can help in several ways: Scenarios can define
279 boundary conditions that are not captured dynamically in models. For example, a model that
280 predicts the consequences of river restoration actions based on trade-offs between ecological and
281 social objectives does not explicitly consider economic trends. Nonetheless, the availability of
282 funds will influence management outcomes considerably. Such information can be part of the
283 scenario narrative. Scenarios can also help reduce uncertainty by testing different spots or
284 trajectories of the uncertain space. To do so, a scenario could be designed taking into account the
285 lower end of a process interval, while an alternate scenario is designed capturing the upper end of

286 the same process. Scenarios of stream flow based on climate forecasts to predict changes in size or
287 frequency of future floods is an example for such an approach. Scenarios can also account for
288 changes which are, in principle, unknown. The dispersal capacities of many species under climate
289 change are examples for that. Markovic et al. (2014) dealt with this challenge assuming two
290 dispersal scenarios when modelling the distribution of freshwater plants, fishes, molluscs, odonates,
291 amphibians, crayfish, and turtles across Europe: an optimistic scenario, assuming free dispersal to
292 suitable catchments and a pessimistic scenario, assuming no-dispersal at all. While the reality likely
293 falls somewhere in between those two scenarios, they are useful to represent two extremes of a
294 continuum of possible outcomes (Franklin, Wejnert, Hathaway, Rochester, & Fisher, 2009).

295 A current challenge for the use of scenarios in EBM planning is that scenarios should
296 address the spatial and temporal scales relevant for management and for the dynamics of the
297 modelled system. Thereby, the temporal scale of processes in social-ecological systems can vary
298 considerably. For example, when long-term management actions are envisaged, it might be better to
299 develop a series of shorter-term scenarios to reduce uncertainty and allow for further refinement of
300 processes. Such an approach is appropriate when dealing with species dispersal which might occur
301 rapidly at the onset of an implemented management strategy, but may slow down later (Winking,
302 Lorenz, Sures, & Hering, 2016). On the other hand, climate and biodiversity scenarios are often
303 limited to large scale environmental changes, mainly global or national. Hence, they are not well
304 connected to local decision-making and vice versa (Rosa et al., 2017).

305 A new generation of multiscale scenarios that capture the whole coupled social-ecological
306 system seem to hold promise for EBM planning. Such scenarios not only describe environmental
307 change, but also model how stakeholders may respond to changes in drivers, biodiversity, ESS, and
308 human well-being (Rosa et al., 2017). To develop such scenarios, better knowledge of the links
309 between ecosystems and human well-being is needed. Making a first step in this direction, Venohr
310 et al. (2018) suggest how ecological quality, recreational quality, and management can be
311 conceptually linked in fresh waters.

312

313 *2.5 Planning across realms*

314 Spatial connectivity has long been acknowledged to be pivotal in maintaining natural ecological
315 processes and biodiversity in fresh waters (Pringle, 2001). Hence, concepts and analytical
316 management tools to manage connectivity within catchments exist en masse. Longitudinal
317 connectivity, for example, has been integrated in catchment management approaches to allocate
318 priority conservation areas. Hermoso, Linke, Prenda, & Possingham (2011) were the first to test the
319 effect of connectivity in spatial optimisation analyses. They found that the inclusion of connectivity
320 resulted in whole sub-basins being prioritized as fish conservation areas, rather than just river
321 corridors. Subsequently, longitudinal connectivity has been commonly considered in freshwater

322 conservation planning and to inform management (Langhans, Gessner, Hermoso, & Wolter, 2016).
323 Similarly, lateral connectivity between various freshwater habitats such as lakes and wetlands that
324 are not necessarily directly connected along the river network has also been considered (Hermoso,
325 Kennard, & Linke, 2012).

326 Meeting objectives in freshwater systems alone can compromise the achievement of
327 objectives in other, linked realms, which may lead to substantial trade-offs (Rieman, Hessburg,
328 Luce, & Dare, 2010). Contrarily, planning management actions across connected ecosystems can
329 result in co-benefits, if management achieves objectives in several of them (Adams et al., 2014).
330 Although guidelines for freshwater management highlight the need for integration, only a few
331 cross-realm case studies targeting freshwater-terrestrial (Leonard, Baldwin, & Hanks, 2017) or
332 terrestrial(catchment)-marine systems (Klein et al., 2010) exist to date. Some studies claim to
333 integrate management or conservation across realms, but they only consider some form of
334 influence, for example a threat originating in one realm and how it affects connected realms
335 (Álvarez-Romero, Adams, et al., 2015). One of the cross-realm management plans that has been
336 applied (for the Gulf of California) aimed to identify areas in river catchments for protection or
337 management, specifically to conserve terrestrial biodiversity and, concurrently, maintain coastal-
338 marine water quality downstream (Álvarez-Romero, Pressey, Ban, & Brodie, 2015).

339 Despite progress made in the theory of cross-realm planning, more knowledge is necessary
340 to better understand co-benefits and trade-offs across realms and how socioeconomic interactions
341 can be integrated into planning (Álvarez-Romero, Adams, et al., 2015). In the future, more on-the-
342 ground applications are needed to demonstrate the theoretical advancements and to provide
343 practical guidance.

344

345 *2.6 Evaluating and prioritizing management strategies*

346 Historically, environmental water management focused on effectiveness (i.e. the impact of
347 management on ecological outcomes) and efficiency (i.e. the benefit-to-cost ratio). Hence, there is
348 ample guidance (e.g., concepts, protocols, indicators, and metrics) on how best to achieve
349 ecological targets (Revenga, Campbell, Abell, De Villiers, & Bryer, 2005; Woolsey et al., 2007).

350 The most commonly used approach to maximise efficiency in environmental management is
351 cost-effectiveness analyses. Cost-effectiveness is the degree to which a management strategy is
352 effective in relation to the overall costs, including opportunity costs (Naidoo & Adamowicz, 2006)
353 when implementing the action needed to reach the anticipated outcome. Cost-effectiveness analyses
354 ensure that the cheapest (i.e. least-cost) solution for reaching pre-defined targets is identified,
355 whereas an additional incremental cost analysis reveals how costs increase with increasing target
356 levels – information which can considerably facilitate decision making. Including information on
357 the spatial heterogeneity of conservation or management costs as an input variable to the planning

358 process has been shown to be beneficial for reaching targets at lower costs. For example, Ferraro
359 (2003) found that costs for managing a river catchment in upstate New York to preserve drinking
360 water quality downstream could be considerably reduced when costs (i.e., the acquisition costs of
361 land parcels that contain riparian buffer) and benefits (i.e., the reduction in pollutants and
362 sediments) were considered concurrently instead of benefits alone. In contrast to such monetary
363 costs, Linke et al. (2012) used a cost surrogate (i.e., a landscape measure of catchment disturbance)
364 to prioritize least disturbed conservation areas for fish in the Daly River catchment (Northern
365 Australia). It is therefore just as, or even more important to consider costs in freshwater EBM
366 planning (Carwardine et al., 2008)

367 Recently, a third criteria - social equity - has gained importance in management assessments
368 (Zafra-Calvo et al., 2017). For example, the CBD's Aichi Target 11 that asks for 17 % of inland
369 water to be conserved through effectively and equitably managed systems of protected areas. Social
370 equity refers to fair or just treatment of individuals or groups (Law et al., 2018), and consists of four
371 dimensions (McDermott, Mahanty, & Schreckenberg, 2013): procedure (equal involvement),
372 distribution (of costs, benefits, rights, responsibilities, risks etc.), recognition (respecting knowledge
373 systems, values, social norms etc.), and context (social, environmental, economic, and political
374 history and circumstances). A recent systematic review analysed 139 peer-reviewed studies and
375 found that the majority of conservation actions have negative equity outcomes (Friedman et al.,
376 2018). Hence, we recommend accounting for procedural, recognitional, and contextual dimensions
377 directly during the EBM planning stage. Procedural equity can be addressed either when selecting
378 stakeholders or collaboratively identifying objectives and targets. Distributional equity strongly
379 depends on the choice of management strategy. For example, the morphological rehabilitation of a
380 channelized river reach imposes costs for the local tax payers, whereas improved water quality or
381 flood protection benefit downstream communities. Therefore, the equitable distribution of costs and
382 benefits should be considered as one of the criteria in assessing and prioritizing management
383 strategies. Future projects on-the-ground that include equity as a criteria will provide much needed
384 experience on how to specifically assess the different equity dimensions, and on how they influence
385 the success of a freshwater management strategy.

386 387 *2.7 Spatial planning for biodiversity conservation and ecosystem services*

388 The concept of protected areas is currently moving from almost exclusively biodiversity
389 conservation-driven towards including separate management zones, where additional values, such
390 as ESS must be restored and conserved (Hermoso, Abell, Linke, & Boon, 2016). There is
391 agreement on the benefits of integrating ESS into local and regional landscape planning (Tallis &
392 Polasky, 2009). For example, the CBD's Aichi Target D is to "enhance the benefits to all from

393 biodiversity and ESS". This strategy is increasingly being viewed as necessary to safeguard the
394 critical services that humans receive from biodiversity and ecosystems, but also because it provides
395 an opportunity to find new resources and obtain buy-in from the public for protected areas and
396 conservation (Harrison et al., 2016).

397 Integrating the planning of ESS and freshwater biodiversity is challenging, because securing
398 access to some services might threaten other services or biodiversity directly (Hermoso, Cattarino,
399 Linke, & Kennard, 2018). For example, granting access to fresh water or releasing the hydropower
400 capacity of a river reach might impact not only biodiversity but also the recreation potential within
401 that reach or water purification. On the other hand, there are opportunities to enhance co-benefits
402 between biodiversity and the maintenance of ESS that are more compatible with conservation
403 (Atkinson et al., 2016). For example, protecting and maintaining riparian forest increases carbon
404 storage and flood control, while concurrently benefitting riparian and freshwater biodiversity
405 (Bryan et al., 2016).

406 To ensure that the application of the planning methods is flexible enough in practice and
407 identifies portions of ecosystems that are feasible in managing, Abell, Allan, & Lehner (2007)
408 proposed a multi-zone approach that organises the landscape/riverscape into different management
409 zones under different management regimes. Hermoso, Cattarino, Kennard, Watts, & Linke (2015)
410 tested this approach for the purpose of protecting freshwater fish in the Daly river (northern
411 Australia), i.e. first without considering any ESS to test the efficiency of the approach. Using three
412 different zones (core conservation zones that are connected through critical management zones,
413 buffered upstream by catchment management zones), they found that multi-zonal conservation
414 plans were significantly more efficient. More specifically, the total area in need of strict
415 conservation was reduced by a twofold factor, compared to a single zone approach. In the follow-up
416 study (Hermoso et al., 2018), they then extended the goal of the conservation planning exercise to
417 not only identify priority areas for the conservation of freshwater fish, turtles, and waterbirds in the
418 Daly river, but concurrently for the provision of four freshwater ESS. Two of them, i.e. flood
419 regulation by riparian forests and provision of perennial water, were deemed to be rather compatible
420 with conservation goals, while groundwater provision for agriculture and recreational fisheries were
421 less so. By applying three conservation zones (for biodiversity and compatible ESS) and two
422 production zones (for incompatible ESS), conservation plans achieved up to 53% more co-benefits
423 for low ESS targets, compared to a single-zone approach. In addition, incompatible ESS were
424 represented 56% less often within conservation zones, when ESS targets were set high.

425 Hence, systematic multi-zone plans can help unlock the potential of conservation
426 recommendations for freshwater ecosystems by enhancing the efficiency of a conservation plan.
427 Now, more implementations of such plans are needed to further fine-tune the approach.

428

429 2.8 *Quantifying uncertainties*

430 Due to the lack of a comprehensive understanding of the structure, functioning, and dynamics of
431 freshwater ecosystems in the face of rapid environmental changes, management decisions tend to be
432 based on uncertain knowledge. This is further complicated by uncertainties in stakeholder
433 preferences, uncertainty regarding the predictions of consequences of management actions,
434 uncertainty around feedbacks and stochasticity within the socio-ecological system, and the intrinsic
435 uncertainty of predicting future states. Consequently, uncertainty assessments and the
436 documentation of uncertainty are of particular importance in the context of EBM. For example, the
437 quantified uncertainty of the degree to which a management strategy will fulfil its objectives is
438 information that is important for prioritizing strategies (Reichert & Borsuk, 2005). The full
439 spectrum of uncertainty, however, is rarely accounted for in environmental management because it
440 is impossible to do so. Thus, to be successful EBM requires an iterative process of evaluation and
441 learning in the form of adaptive management coupled with uncertainty quantification. Indeed,
442 successful EBM heavily relies on a transparent assessment of the quality and reliability of each of
443 its components (Clark et al., 2001).

444 Advances in uncertainty quantification have recently been made in environmental modelling
445 (Guisan & Zimmermann, 2000). Main sources of uncertainty in models are those relating to model
446 inputs, model structure (i.e. process uncertainty), and model parameters (Knutti, 2008). Model
447 inputs in the form of ecological measurements almost always have large measurement errors and
448 data limitations. Taking advantage of citizen science programs, the increasing availability of
449 automated measuring technologies as well as quality control procedures, can greatly improve data
450 quality and quantity and reduce input uncertainty (Harmel, Cooper, Slade, Haney, & Arnold, 2006;
451 Vermeiren, Munoz, Zimmer, & Sheaves, 2016). For example, Creek Watch pairs citizen scientists
452 with smartphone applications to fill data gaps in freshwater monitoring and has been useful in
453 improving current water management practices (Kim et al., 2011). Uncertainty in model structure
454 often results from incomplete knowledge of the system or competing theories, and the need to
455 simplify model structure (Knutti, 2008). Models using artificial intelligence can overcome a lack of
456 system understanding but are often difficult for the average practitioner or policy maker to
457 understand and require a lot of data to run (Lek & Guegan, 1999). Therefore, they are a challenge to
458 apply in practice. Given the long history of both managing and studying fresh waters, uncertainty in
459 model structure could be reduced with increased collaboration among scientists and managers.
460 Parameter uncertainty also stems from incomplete system knowledge. The recently increased
461 attention to Bayesian approaches can be useful in this context, since they formulate parameter
462 distributions rather than single point estimates of parameter values (Ellison, 2004). In addition,
463 Bayesian inference uses prior knowledge to balance uncertainty in input data. Moreover, when
464 combined with empirical data Bayesian inference allows updating of current knowledge (Charniak,

465 1991), which fits well in an adaptive management context. Overall, we see a high potential for
466 Bayesian techniques in EBM, especially with the increasing availability of computational power.

467

468 3. A WORKFLOW FOR OPERATIONALIZING EBM PLANNING

469 Based on the innovations of the eight research areas and the concept of how they contribute to
470 freshwater management (Fig. 1), a workflow for operationalizing the EBM-planning stage was
471 developed. The complete workflow requires substantial data and resourcing. Hence, depending on
472 the environmental problem, the available data, and resources and/or time constraints, its application
473 may not be feasible. In such situations, one of the two less complex versions of the workflow which
474 are introduced below, may be applied.

475 The complete workflow consists of nine steps (Fig. 2) and starts with the two sets of
476 distribution layers: one for biodiversity and one for ESS. SDMs are used to model the respective
477 biodiversity distribution at time $t = 0$ (Fig. 2; **step 1**). SDMs use the occurrence records of species
478 and the environmental conditions at those same locations to assess the species ~ environment
479 relationship and project a range-wide, probabilistic habitat-suitability index onto the study area
480 (Elith & Leathwick, 2009). SDMs can be based on a wide range of correlative to mechanistic
481 algorithms (Guisan & Zimmermann, 2000) and can be developed to output either a single
482 community index or predictions for individual species. The appropriate choice of the modelling
483 method needs to consider the requirements of the EBM plan and the available input data, existing
484 knowledge on the freshwater system, the optimal level of model complexity, and the computational
485 demand. Correlative models are often convenient, since they can handle the type of data that is most
486 often available: opportunistic point records combined with environmental covariates. Additionally,
487 at large spatial and temporal scales where national or provincial management decisions are made,
488 static correlative models can deliver an acceptable explanatory power, yielding informative results
489 tailored to the scale and timeframe of the EBM plan. However, their reduced consideration of
490 mechanistic understanding could limit their power (Guisan & Zimmermann, 2000). Mechanistic
491 models also have limitations, most notably that they require more detailed data and knowledge of
492 the system, often resulting in these models being applied at smaller spatial scales.

493 In parallel to step 1, ESS models are developed. To do so, one can choose from many
494 different methodologies (see Domisch et al. (2017) for a comprehensive list and detailed
495 description). One powerful software platform is ARIES (ARTificial Intelligence for Ecosystem
496 Services), which integrates multiple modelling paradigms for spatio-temporal modelling and
497 mapping of ESS. The methodology uses artificial intelligence features, such as semantics and
498 machine learning for model selection and assembly to quantify ESS flows from ecosystems to
499 beneficiaries (Villa et al., 2014). Another commonly used software is InVEST (Integrated Valuation
500 of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs), which also allows spatial mapping and modelling of

501 multiple ESS. It includes a diverse set of provisioning, regulating, and cultural services from marine
502 and terrestrial environments. The models primarily provide results in biophysical terms, to which
503 valuations can be applied (Sharp et al., 2018).

504 After having established the models for biodiversity and ESS, experts select and combine
505 external scenarios, ideally together with stakeholders (**step 2**). The scenarios must consider spatial
506 and temporal scales that are relevant for the management targets and for the dynamics of the
507 modelled system. The scenarios used in the model analysis need to be defined (i.e., explorative,
508 normative, descriptive) and justified. If the goal is to learn more about uncertain processes and to
509 explore risks, it is advisable to develop extreme scenarios for exploration and learning purposes.
510 However, if the goal is to narrow down the environmental effects on particular species
511 developments, one should choose scenarios that predict expected environmental changes accurately
512 at the species relevant scales.

513 Environmental variables are projected according to the external scenarios. Then, they are
514 included in the statistical relationship to forecast species and ESS distributions for each of the
515 scenarios (**step 3**). Experts and stakeholders identify biodiversity and ESS targets according to
516 policies and subjective preferences. Additional socio-ecological targets that are particularly
517 important to the community can also be included and quantified here (**step 4**). System deficits can
518 now be identified for each scenario, by comparing projected species and ESS distributions with the
519 pre-defined targets (**step 5**).

520 With the deficits for biodiversity and ESS laid out, a set of potential management strategies
521 that potentially reach the identified targets for biodiversity and ESS objectives, are developed -
522 ideally in collaboration with stakeholders (**step 6**). Management strategies entail actions that, if
523 implemented, will help meet the socio-ecologic objectives and targets identified for the respective
524 system. To compare the effect of different management strategies, first baseline (i.e., business as
525 usual) scenarios are used to predict the future state of a freshwater system given external scenarios
526 and current management practices. The strength of the analyses of baseline scenarios is to identify
527 deficits and, hence, the key challenges which are translated into management objectives. The
528 management strategies entail alternative management actions to achieve these management
529 objectives, which allows predicting the consequences of the different strategies for biodiversity and
530 ESS under the different external scenarios (**step 7**). Comparing the assessments of the predicted
531 consequences of different management strategies, based on effectiveness, efficiency, and social
532 equity, will enhance the understanding of leverage points and will show uncertainties. This, in turn,
533 will ultimately aid in the identification of the most robust strategy. Stakeholder involvement is
534 crucial in the development of management strategies to ensure realism and acceptance for further
535 implementation (Talley, Schneider, & Lindquist, 2016) (**step 8**).

536 Spatially-explicit biodiversity and ESS data, predicted from the optimal management
537 scenario, are used for the spatial planning of the EBM following the principles of systematic
538 conservation planning (**step 9**). Different softwares widely used in conservation planning have
539 begun to be applied to planning processes, such as holistic management planning. These plans go
540 beyond biodiversity conservation and try to integrate other objectives such as the use of natural
541 resources (Levin et al., 2013). The software packages optimize the spatial allocation of biodiversity
542 conservation and ESS delivery areas across the respective area to be managed (optimally across
543 freshwater, coastal, and marine zones), while minimizing cost and maximizing targets for the
544 management plan (Hermoso et al., 2018). Two examples of planning software are Marxan with
545 Zones (Watts et al., 2009) and Gurobi (Beyer, Dujardin, Watts, & Possingham, 2016). Marxan with
546 Zones (Watts et al., 2009) is an extension of Marxan (Ball, Possingham, & Watts, 2009), which is
547 currently the most utilised planning software worldwide. Marxan with Zones allows the planner to
548 specify different management zones, each of which can be characterized by actions, objectives, and
549 restraints. One zone is usually the no-take or conservation only zone, while others would allow for
550 ESS use. Besides optimizing for costs, the software can be used to emphasise specific features of
551 the management plan by giving different weights to different ESS and/or different costs to each
552 management zone. In addition, irreplaceable areas that, for example, contain critically endangered
553 species or culturally significant values which should not be traded-off in the optimisation, can be
554 locked into the management plan. Gurobi uses the same input files as Marxan, but is based on
555 integer linear programming which has been shown to out-compete traditional simulated annealing
556 tools (as used in Marxan) in terms of time and accuracy (Beyer et al., 2016).

557 The products of step 9 are EBM plans which inform decision makers and stakeholders. The
558 plans may need to be refined according when new input data become available, and recalculated
559 until a plan has been agreed on. Step 9 concludes the EBM-planning stage (see Fig. 1 for the
560 additional components needed to build a full EBM-cycle, i.e. adaptive management).

561

562

563 **Figure 2.** The nine steps of the workflow that integrate the methodological advancements in the
 564 respective research areas. Executing the workflow helps structure and operationalize the EBM-
 565 planning stage and leads to the identification of a spatially optimized management plan.

566

567 4. THE LIGHT AND ULTRALIGHT VERSIONS OF THE WORKFLOW

568 The main difference between the full and the light version of the workflow is that the light one does
 569 not consider future trends, disregarding external scenarios (Fig. 3). Hence, deficits are identified
 570 based on the present status of species and ESS distributions and potential management strategies are
 571 developed accordingly. The steps that follow remain the same as explained for the full workflow.
 572 Excluding external scenarios simplifies the workflow, since less stakeholder involvement is needed
 573 and fewer models have to be built. On the downside, the light version of the workflow bases
 574 recommendations only on present distributions of biodiversity and ESS. In the future, depending on
 575 the location of the system in question, these recommendations may become irrelevant when species
 576 and ESS redistribute in response to climate change or other drivers (Pecl et al., 2017). Additionally,
 577 the time interval between action planning, implementation, and actually observing a change in the
 578 managed system may be decades (Kail, Brabec, Poppe, & Januschke, 2015). Hence, considering
 579 future distributions of biodiversity and ESS may be crucial for establishing a cost-effective
 580 management process and is, therefore, highly recommended.

582

583 **Figure 3.** The less complex workflow (light version) is based on the current status of biodiversity
 584 and ESS, considering different management strategies that are evaluated and ranked according to
 585 relevant criteria.

586

587 Compared to the light version, the ultralight version does not consider external scenarios or
 588 potential management strategies (Fig. 4). Similar to the light one, it is based on present biodiversity
 589 and ESS distributions. However, instead of potential management strategies, stakeholders identify
 590 different management zones that they wish to be considered in the respective system. Abell et al.
 591 (2007) proposes three potential zones: (1) the freshwater focal zone, which is dedicated to the
 592 protection of a specific freshwater feature, (2) the critical management zone, which needs to be
 593 managed in a way that ensures the functionality of the focal area, and (3) the catchment
 594 management zone, which contains the entire upstream catchment of a critical management zone
 595 (see above). The inclusion of management zones when spatially optimising biodiversity and ESS
 596 delivery areas allows accounting for trade-offs and co-benefits between biodiversity and different
 597 ESS. Hence, it helps diffuse concerns of blocking away essential ESS for the sake of biodiversity
 598 conservation. This version of the workflow may be the preferred option to apply when time and
 599 money are constrained or if a management strategy has already been agreed upon. However

600 likewise to the light version, the ultralight approach cannot be used to develop recommendations for
 601 the future nor does it evaluate and rank different, alternative management strategies.
 602

603
 604 **Figure 4.** The least complex workflow (ultralight version) considers the present status of biodiversity and ESS and different management zones (*sensu* Abell et al., 2007).
 605
 606

607 4. SYNOPSIS

608 The novelty of this study lies in the combination of eight well known research areas that in concert
 609 allows better planning, operationalization, and eventually implementation of EBM in freshwater
 610 ecosystems. The proposed workflow helps operationalize the EBM-planning stage under
 611 consideration of the many different objectives freshwater management has, such as spatial
 612 optimization, cost-efficiency, social equity, achievement of conservation and/or ESS targets, and
 613 maintenance of irreplaceable biodiversity or cultural values among others. In addition, it facilitates
 614 integration between disciplines of knowledge at multiple spatial and temporal scales and among
 615 policies. It is not intended to be a rigid blueprint - instead it is an iterative procedure that can be
 616 modified to account for new information and localized changes depending on the freshwater
 617 systems to be managed. Due to the documented success of EBM in the marine realm, we believe
 618 that our study will provide the means to foster applications of EBM in fresh waters, improve
 619 management effectiveness, and create socio-ecological benefits through buy-in from the
 620 community.

621
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632

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